

Patterns of variation in wing venation of Iberian *Cordulegaster boltonii* (Donovan, 1807) (Odonata: Cordulegastridae)

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Research Article

OPEN ACCESS

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Published: 10 November 2023

Received: 31 January 2023

Accepted: 29 October 2023

Citation:

Nunes, Santamaría, Casanueva, Sánchez-Sastre, Ferreras-Romero, Romero, Hernández & Campos (2023):

Patterns of variation in wing venation of Iberian *Cordulegaster boltonii* (Donovan, 1807) (Odonata: Cordulegastridae). *International Journal of Odonatology*, 26, 164–171
doi:10.48156/1388.2023.1917226

Data Availability Statement:

All relevant data are within the paper and its [Supporting Information files](#).

Abstract. Some structural characters, such as wing venation, have been used in odonates to differentiate taxa. In *Cordulegaster boltonii*, a species widely distributed throughout the western Palaearctic, the main characteristics of its wing venation have not been quantified until now. A six-variable analysis of wing venation (number of antenodal and postnodal cross-veins, number of cells in the anal triangle and in the anal loop) in specimens from several European countries was carried out. The results showed that: (a) females had a greater number of transversal veins and cells in the anal loop than males; (b) the values of these four variables were significantly lower in males from the Iberian Peninsula than in those from elsewhere; (c) within the Iberian Peninsula two groups of populations can be distinguished: one covers the north and the other the rest of the peninsula, the latter with two subgroups, one in the centre and one in the south and east. The number of cells in the anal loop is a valid variable for analyzing geographic differences in this species.

Key words. Anisoptera, dragonflies, Iberian Peninsula, odonates, wings

Introduction

Patterns of body coloration (Mayr & Ashlock, 1991) have been used in some genera of Odonata, e.g., *Cordulegaster* Leach, 1815, for differentiating species (Abbott & Hibbitts, 2011; Boudot, 2001; Corso, 2019). Characters based on coloration can be controlled by various genes, some of which may be expressed or not depending on environmental conditions (Sánchez-Guillén et al., 2005), so that it would appear preferable to use structural characteristics instead.

Among the structural characteristics, the wings of odonates present particularly elaborate vein patterns (Hoffman et al., 2018), which have been used for phylogenetic and systematic analyses (e.g., Carle & Kjer, 2002; Ninomiya & Yoshizawa,

2009; Trueman, 1996; Rehn, 2003). In recent decades such analyses have been largely—but not entirely—superseded by genetic analyses (e.g., Bybee et al., 2008; Dijkstra & Kalkman, 2012; Kohli et al., 2021; Suhling et al., 2015; Suvorov et al., 2022). The functioning of the odonates' wings has been extensively studied (e.g., Blanke, 2018; Norberg, 1972; Wootton 1991, 1992). Some wing structures, such as anal loop, anal triangle, and node position, have been used to distinguish taxa (e.g., Abbott, 2006; Carle & Kjer, 2002; Tillyard, 1917). Other structural characteristics, such as male reproductive appendages (hamuli) and anal appendages, are also used because they can be species-specific (Corbet, 2004). In some *Cordulegaster* species, differentiation based on these structures agreed with that based on genetic characteristics (Pilgrim et al., 2002). However, in other species, a clear discordance was found between phylogeny based on morphological characteristics and one suggested by genetic characters (Huang et al., 2020; Sánchez-Herrera et al., 2020).

The genus *Cordulegaster* includes 30 species distributed throughout the northern hemisphere (Schorr & Paulson, 2020). Two main groups of species have been established: *boltonii* and *bidentata*, distinguishable mainly by characteristics of their abdominal appendages (Askew, 2004; Dijkstra & Lewington, 2006).

Cordulegaster boltonii is distributed throughout the Western Palaearctic (Boudot & Holuša, 2015). In the Iberian Peninsula, it occupies all mountain ranges, and up to four subspecies differentiated by morphological characteristics have been described from southwestern Europe: *C. b. boltonii*, *C. b. immaculifrons*, *C. b. iberica*, and *C. b. algerica* (Boudot, 2001; Boudot & Jacquemin, 1995). However, more recent work has demonstrated that the validity of these subspecies does not have genetic support (Froufe et al., 2014), but the genes analyzed by Froufe et al. are likely not linked to those that produce the different chromatypes. Until this situation is clarified, it seems preferable to speak of *C. boltonii* morphs rather than of subspecies.

The morphology of *C. boltonii* has been extensively studied. Ocharan (1989) demonstrated that there is individual variability in adult coloration. A biometric analysis carried out using exuviae revealed that the Iberian populations are distributed in four distinguishable areas: northern, central, east and middle-south, and southernmost (Casanueva et al., 2020). On the other hand, Hernández et al. (2022) showed that latitude, altitude, and environmental temperature are significantly correlated with the sizes of some exuviant body parts. Based on these last two studies, it might therefore be possible that some adult structural characteristics can also be useful for differentiating Iberian populations. In the Iberian Peninsula there is a great diversity of environments and climatic conditions, as the northern parts belong to the Euro-Siberian region, and a much larger area, occupying the centre and south, is ascribed to the Mediterranean region (Rivas-Martínez, 1987). Both feature mountain ranges with populations of *C. bolto-*

nii that must have adapted to different environmental conditions.

The aim of this paper is to show, using structural characteristics of the wing venation, the level of differentiation existing between *C. boltonii* specimens from six Iberian areas, and possible differences with respect to specimens from populations residing in other European countries.

Material and methods

Our analyses were carried out on adult specimens of *C. boltonii* from 15 entomological collections, both private and in museums, representing ten European countries in which *C. boltonii* occurs (Supplementary Material 1). Of each specimen, the fore- and hindwings were photographed, while track was kept to which collection it belonged, whenever possible.

In the Iberian Peninsula, six distribution zones were selected according to: (a) the geographical distribution of the species, which mainly occupies mountain ranges (Boudot & Holuša, 2015), although it may also occupy non-mountainous areas (Ocharan & Torralba-Burrial, 2004); (b) the groups recovered by means of the biogeographical analysis of *C. boltonii* carried out by Casanueva et al. (2020); and (c) the availability of specimens in the entomological collections reviewed. These six zones have been specified as “Pyrenees”, “Cantabrian Mountains”, “Central System”, “Central Portugal”, “Iberian System”, and “Sierra Nevada”, respectively (Fig. 1). The first two belong to the Euro-Siberian region, and the other four to the Mediterranean region. Specimens from several localities in each zone (from 11 to 64 localities, see Supplementary Material 2) were analyzed.

We follow the wing terminology of Riek & Kukalová-Peck (1984) as updated by Rehn (2003). Six characteristics were analyzed for each specimen: in the hindwing, the number of cells in the anal triangle (AT) (males only) and the anal loop (AL), and in fore- and hindwings, number of antenodal (Ax) and postnodal (Px) cross-veins (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the nodal index (NI) was calculated as $NI = Ax/Px$ (Fraser, 1934). This index was used in *Cordulegaster* by Fraser (1936) to describe species.

In the analysis of geographic differences, only male specimens were used, because females do not have an anal triangle, and the venation of their wings differs from that of males (see below). The use of male specimens only has proved informative in odonates for specific differentiation using the *hamuli*, which are also absent in females (Leong & Hafernack, 1992).

To identify the level of population homogeneity existing within each of the six Iberian areas was compared, calculating the diversity of the number of cells in the anal loop in specimens from each zone with the Shannon-Wiener index ($H' = -\sum p_i \cdot \ln p_i$), where p_i is the proportion of the item 'i' in the total number of specimens.

Using Past 3.15 software (Hammer et al., 2001), a clustered multivariate analysis was performed that

seeks to group the variables in a quest to achieve the maximum homogeneity in each group and show up the greatest difference between the groups. In this analysis, the Unweighted Pair-Group Average (UPGMA) was used as the algorithm, and the Euclidean and constrained distances as the similarity index. Clusters were joined based on the average distance between all members in the two groups. With a bootstrapping of $N = 10,000$, the percentage of support is given in each of the nodes.

An ANOVA (ANalysis Of VAriance) was performed with the STATA 12.1 software between the studied zones for each of the variables, after verifying that the normality and homogeneity of the variance were met. If this was not met, the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis analysis was performed. Pairwise comparisons were also made with the STATA 12.1 software for the variables in which significant differences were found between specimens from different areas of the Iberian Peninsula.

Results

A total of 679 adult specimens of *C. boltonii* (588 males, 91 females) were analyzed. Of these, 127 (105 males, 22 females) were from outside the Iberian Peninsula and 552 (483 males, 69 females) from the Iberian Peninsula.

Differences between the sexes

The average numbers of both antenodal and postnodal cross-veins of fore- and hindwings, and of cells in the

anal loop of the hindwing were significantly lower in males than in females (Table 1). Therefore, these variables must be analyzed separately for males and females. In contrast, the nodal index (NI) values for both fore- and hindwings were statistically similar in both sexes. Since the females lack an anal triangle, only male specimens were analyzed.

Differences between Iberian vs. non-Iberian male specimens

Average values of all measured variables differed significantly between Iberian and non-Iberian males (Table 2). The numbers of antenodal and postnodal cross-veins in fore- and hindwings were consistently higher in specimens from outside Iberia (Fig. 3). Likewise, the numbers of cells inside the anal triangle and anal loop were higher in specimens from outside Iberia (Fig. 4). However, specimens from within the Iberian Peninsula had higher nodal index (NI) values than those from outside Iberia.

The number of cells of the anal loop (AL) varied between three and ten (Table 1). Only seven specimens from outside Iberia had more than seven cells in the anal loop (Table 3). In the six Iberian zones, anal loops with five cells were the most common configuration, but the frequencies of each class differed significantly between zones ($\chi^2 = 141.82, p < 0.0001, 30 \text{ d.f.}$). The highest value of cell class diversity (from 3 to > 7), calculated according to the Shannon index, was obtained in the heterogeneous group of specimens from outside Iberia, and the lowest in Central Portugal (Table 3), but the number of samples studied from this last zone was small ($n = 16$).

Figure 1. Sampling zones. (1) Pyrenees (dark blue dots); (2) Cantabrian Mountains (green dots); (3) Central System (red dots); (4) Central Portugal (pink dots); (5) Iberian System (yellow dots); (6) Sierra Nevada (pale blue dots). Dendrogram with the sampling zones in the Iberian Peninsula. Numbers at nodes indicate bootstrap support for that particular branch.

Table 1. Mean values (\pm SD) of analyzed variables in male and female *Cordulegaster boltonii*. n: sample size; Ax: antenodal cross-veins; Px: postnodal cross-veins; NI: nodal index as Ax/Px; AT: number of cells in the anal triangle; AL: number of cells in the anal loop. Range of values in brackets. F: ANOVA; KW: Kruskal-Wallis test; p: probability.

	n	Forewing			Hindwing				
		Ax	Px	NI	Ax	Px	NI	AT	AL
Males	588	18.25 \pm 1.30 (14–22)	13.45 \pm 1.67 (8–19)	1.37 \pm 0.16 (0.94–1.88)	12.85 \pm 1.11 (9–16)	13.08 \pm 1.60 (8–17)	0.99 \pm 0.13 (0.69–1.50)	4.37 \pm 0.86 (2–7)	5.06 \pm 0.93 (3–10)
Females	91	19.88 \pm 1.52 (17–23)	15.06 \pm 1.77 (11–19)	1.34 \pm 0.16 (0.95–1.92)	13.92 \pm 1.11 (12–17)	14.30 \pm 1.64 (11–19)	0.98 \pm 0.11 (0.63–1.33)		7.76 \pm 1.40 (5–12)
Test		KW = 75.522	F _{1,633} = 65.58	KW = 3.34	F _{1,677} = 73.84	F _{1,677} = 45.20	KW = 0.076		KW = 188.907
p		0.0001	<0.0001	0.068	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.7827		0.0001

Table 2. Mean values (\pm SD) of analyzed variables in male *Cordulegaster boltonii* from Iberia vs. out of Iberia. n: sample size; Ax: antenodal cross-veins; Px: postnodal cross-veins; NI: nodal index as Ax/Px; AT: number of cells in the anal triangle; AL: number of cells in the anal loop. Range of values in brackets. F: ANOVA; KW: Kruskal-Wallis test; p: probability.

	n	Forewing			Hindwing				
		Ax	Px	NI	Ax	Px	NI	AT	AL
Iberia	483	18.06 \pm 1.27 (14–22)	13.19 \pm 1.59 (8–19)	1.38 \pm 0.16 (0.94–1.88)	12.71 \pm 1.07 (9–15)	12.85 \pm 1.53 (8–17)	1.00 \pm 0.13 (0.69–1.50)	4.28 \pm 0.83 (2–7)	4.90 \pm 0.78 (3–7)
Out of Iberia	105	19.14 \pm 1.03 (16–22)	14.69 \pm 1.49 (11–18)	1.30 \pm 0.19 (1.06–1.67)	13.48 \pm 1.09 (11–16)	14.12 \pm 1.47 (10–17)	0.96 \pm 0.11 (0.71–1.18)	4.85 \pm 0.86 (3–7)	5.80 \pm 1.16 (4–10)
Test		KW = 62.328	F _{1,574} = 75.95	KW = 18.15	F _{1,586} = 43.98	F _{1,586} = 59.78	KW = 5.654	KW = 27.397	KW = 54.786
p		0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0174	0.0001	0.0001

Differences between males of the six Iberian zones compared

Inside the Iberian Peninsula, the number of postnodal (Px) cross-veins and the nodal index (NI) differed between zones both in the forewing and the hindwing (Table 4). The number of antenodal (Ax) cross-veins in the forewing and the number of cells in the anal loop (AL) varied between zones, too (Table 4). The highest average values of Ax, Px, and AL were recorded in the Cantabrian Mountains. On the other hand, the average number of cells in the anal triangle (AT) was similar throughout the six zones analyzed.

To detect similarities between zones of the Iberian Peninsula, a dendrogram based on the significant variables of forewing (Ax, Px, NI) and hindwing (Px, NI, AL) (Table 4) was created. The six zones are distributed in two groups, one formed by the Pyrenees and Cantabrian Mountains, and the other by remaining four zones (Fig. 1). Pairwise comparisons revealed that males from the Pyrenees and Cantabrian Mountains differ from each other in Px of both forewing ($t = 4.49, p < 0.001$) and hindwing ($t = 5.46, p < 0.001$), but not in the other variables ($p > 0.05$). In the second group, Central System and Central Portugal showed high similarity to each other, and the same was the case for the Iberian System and Sierra Nevada.

Figure 2. The hindwing of a *Cordulegaster boltonii* adult male. AT, anal triangle; AL, anal loop; Ax, antenodal cross-veins; Px, postnodal cross-veins.

Table 3. Number of *Cordulegaster boltonii* males (in brackets, percentage) as per number of cells in the anal loop. H': diversity (Shannon's index).

Zone	Number of cells in the anal loop						Total	H'
	3	4	5	6	7	> 7		
Out of Iberia	2 (2.1)	5 (5.3)	35 (37.2)	36 (38.3)	9 (9.6)	7 (7.4)	94	1.39
Pyrenees	4 (5.9)	8 (11.8)	44 (64.7)	12 (17.6)	0	0	68	1.01
Cantabrian Mountains	1 (0.8)	13 (10.2)	77 (60.6)	28 (22.0)	8 (6.3)	0	127	1.08
Central System	4 (3.6)	34 (30.6)	62 (55.9)	9 (8.1)	2 (6.3)	0	111	1.08
Central Portugal	0	2 (12.5)	13 (81.3)	1 (6.3)	0	0	16	0.60
Iberian System	4 (4.8)	21 (25.0)	46 (54.8)	11 (13.1)	2 (2.4)	0	84	1.18
Sierra Nevada	6 (8.3)	25 (34.7)	34 (47.2)	6 (8.3)	1 (1.4)	0	72	1.20

Table 4. Mean values (\pm SD) of analyzed variables in male *Cordulegaster boltonii* from six Iberian sampling zones: (1) Pyrenees; (2) Cantabrian Mountains; (3) Central System; (4) Central Portugal; (5) Iberian System; (6) Sierra Nevada. n: simple size; Ax: antenodal cross-veins; Px: postnodal cross-veins; NI: nodal index as Ax/Px; AT: number of cells in the anal triangle; AL: number of cells in the anal loop. Range of values in brackets. F: ANOVA; KW: Kruskal-Wallis test; p: probability.

Zone	n	Forewing			Hindwing				
		Ax	Px	NI	Ax	Px	NI	AT	AL
1	70	18.06 \pm 1.19 (16–21)	13.06 \pm 1.42 (10–16)	1.40 \pm 0.16 (1.06–1.73)	12.66 \pm 1.21 (10–15)	12.54 \pm 1.34 (8–16)	1.02 \pm 0.15 (0.77–1.50)	4.26 \pm 0.77 (3–6)	4.94 \pm 0.72 (3–6)
2	127	18.44 \pm 1.38 (14–22)	14.06 \pm 1.75 (9–19)	1.33 \pm 0.15 (0.94–1.80)	12.87 \pm 1.02 (10–15)	13.71 \pm 1.59 (10–17)	0.95 \pm 0.12 (0.69–1.27)	4.39 \pm 0.86 (2–7)	5.23 \pm 0.75 (3–7)
3	115	17.96 \pm 1.22 (16–21)	13.06 \pm 1.32 (10–16)	1.39 \pm 0.14 (1.07–1.80)	12.75 \pm 1.18 (9–15)	12.69 \pm 1.43 (9–15)	1.02 \pm 0.14 (0.73–1.50)	4.23 \pm 0.80 (3–6)	4.75 \pm 0.72 (3–7)
4	16	17.75 \pm 1.53 (15–20)	13.50 \pm 1.75 (11–17)	1.33 \pm 0.14 (1.12–1.54)	12.56 \pm 0.96 (11–14)	13.19 \pm 1.42 (11–16)	0.96 \pm 0.14 (0.75–1.18)	4.31 \pm 0.70 (3–5)	4.94 \pm 0.44 (4–6)
5	83	17.84 \pm 1.11 (15–20)	12.32 \pm 1.24 (8–15)	1.46 \pm 0.14 (1.20–1.88)	12.45 \pm 0.97 (10–15)	12.11 \pm 1.39 (9–16)	1.04 \pm 0.13 (0.69–1.30)	4.40 \pm 0.85 (3–7)	4.84 \pm 0.82 (3–7)
6	72	17.86 \pm 1.23 (15–21)	12.94 \pm 1.47 (10–17)	1.40 \pm 0.16 (1.06–1.80)	12.74 \pm 0.92 (11–15)	12.72 \pm 1.28 (10–16)	1.01 \pm 0.11 (0.75–1.27)	4.07 \pm 0.83 (3–6)	4.60 \pm 0.82 (3–7)
Test		F _{5,473} = 3.56	KW = 59.418	KW = 40.129	F _{5,477} = 1.75	KW = 59.401	KW = 28.373	F _{5,477} = 1.81	KW = 31.53
p		0.0036	0.0001	0.0001	0.1221	0.0001	0.0001	0.1088	0.0001

Discussion

According to Wootton (2020), *C. boltonii* is a hawking species, i.e., it needs high flight speed to capture its prey. This speed can be obtained with greater wings length, since in odonata, long wings favour high-speed manoeuvrability. On the other hand, in anisopteran species, some wing areas influence wing shape and therefore flight mode (Blanke, 2018; Rajabi et al., 2016). The basal part of the hindwing helps to reduce the cost of flapping (Wootton, 2020), which means that species that make persistent and unbroken flights have a larger anal region than those that move less (Huang et al., 2020; Suárez-Tovar & Sarmiento, 2016). In the

hindwing, the anal loop provides support to the anal region. Adult males of *C. boltonii* carry out numerous patrol flights daily over the streams they inhabit (Corbet, 2004), having a wide basal zone in their hindwings that lowers energy costs.

During the Quaternary glaciations, numerous species from central and northern Europe took refuge in areas of southern Europe (Hewitt, 2000; Schmitt, 2007), and the Iberian Peninsula was one of the most important refuges for both vertebrates and invertebrates (Gómez & Lunt, 2007). Although little geographical differentiation is presently observed, a moderate genetic diversity within *C. boltonii* suggests that large populations survived in diverse refugia during the last Ice Ages (Froufe et al., 2014).

Likewise, it has been suggested that in the past, the Iberian and North African populations of some species of Odonata and other insects were represented by common ancestors (Cabrero-Sañudo & Lobo, 2006; Ojeda et al., 2021; Simonsen et al., 2020; Todisco et al., 2010).

Males and females of *C. boltonii* differ in external adult morphology (Dijkstra & Lewington, 2006) and larval biometry (Casanueva et al., 2020; Ferreras-Romero & Corbet, 1999). Our data show that they also differ in wing venation. Furthermore, the wing venation of Iberian populations of *C. boltonii* differs from that found in populations outside the Iberian Peninsula.

The climate in the Iberian east and south is similar to that of North Africa. This fact may explain why their odonatofauna host a greater abundance of Ethiopian elements than that of northern Iberia on the one, and a lower proportion of Euro-Siberian elements on the other hand (Fontana-Bria et al., 2017). Our results demonstrate that the *C. boltonii* specimens from the Cantabrian Mountains and Pyrenees, the two northern zones (Euro-Siberians) studied in this work, appear grouped in our analysis and are separated from those from the four Mediterranean zones.

Recently, Santamaría et al. (2022) found that the numbers of cells in the anal triangle and the anal loop in Iberian *C. boltonii* were positively correlated with wing length, and the number of postnodal cross-veins was positively correlated with postnodal length. In the Iberian areas compared in this work, the highest number of postnodal cross-veins was recorded in the Cantabrian Mountains, and the highest number of cells in

the anal loop was recorded in the north (Pyrenees and Cantabrian Mountains) and west (Central Portugal). Conversely, the average number of cells in the anal triangle was similar throughout the six zones analyzed.

In the present study, the highest average values of Ax in the forewing, Px in both wings, and the number of cells in the AL of the hindwing were found in the Cantabrian Mountains (Zone 2). According to Boudot (2001), all populations existing in that zone belong to the nominate subspecies *C. b. boltonii*. On the other hand, the result of the clustered multivariate analysis does not allow to identify clear relationships between the remaining three Iberian subspecies proposed by Boudot (2001) and the other five population groups here studied.

Genetic analyses of several species of the genus *Cordulegaster* present in the western Palaearctic (Froufe

Figure 3. Boxplot of the number of cross-veins in the forewing and hindwing for the seven *Cordulegaster boltonii* zones analysed. Sampling zones: (0) Out of Iberian Peninsula; (1) Pyrenees; (2) Cantabrian Mountains; (3) Central System, 4) Central Portugal, 5) Iberian System, 6) Sierra Nevada. Blue: antennal cross-veins in forewing; red: postnodal cross-veins in forewing; green: postnodal cross-veins in hindwing; yellow: postnodal cross-veins in hindwing. Bars: upper and lower values. Boxes: upper (75%) and lower (25%) percentiles. Line in box: median.

Figure 4. Boxplot of: (A) nodal index values in forewing (blue) and hindwing (yellow); (B) number of cells into the anal triangle (blue) and anal loop (yellow), for the seven sampling zones. (0) Out of Iberian Peninsula; (1) Pyrenees; (2) Cantabrian Mountains; (3) Central System; (4) Central Portugal; (5) Iberian System; (6) Sierra Nevada. Bars: upper and lower values. Boxes: upper (75%) and lower (25%) percentiles. Line in box: median.

et al., 2014) support the validity only of the subspecies *C. boltonii algerica* for populations from northern Africa. The results obtained in this work agree only partially with the above, since certain differentiations in wing venation seem to have occurred between the northern areas (Pyrenees and Cantabrian Mountains) and the rest of Iberia.

Finally, this work once again underscores the importance of museum collections, which continue to be useful for the study of intraspecific diversity (Short et al., 2018), either from a genetic (Mandrioli, 2008) or from other points of view (Suarez & Tsutsui, 2004).

Acknowledgements

We wish to express our gratitude to the people who facilitated our visits to collections, especially Araceli Anadón (Departamento de Biología de Organismos y Sistemas, Oviedo, Spain), Arturo Ariño and David Galicia (Museo de Ciencias de la Universidad de Navarra, Pamplona, Spain), Ben Price and Joana Cristovão (Natural History Museum United Kingdom, London, Great Britain), Cristina Rufino (Museum of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal), Enrique Fernández Carrillo and José Luis Fernández Carrillo (Ciudad Real, Spain), Ibón de Olano (Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Álava, Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain), Joaquim Baixeras (Instituto Cavanilles de Biodiversidad, Valencia, Spain), José Grosso (Museu de História Natural e da Ciência da Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal), Luca Bartolozzi (Museo di Storia Naturale, La Specola, Firenze, Italy), Manuel Tierno de Figueroa (Universidad de Granada, Granada, Spain), Mercedes Paris (Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain), and Roberto A. Keller (National Museum of Natural History and Science, Lisboa, Portugal). The National Park and Natural Park of Sierra Nevada and the Regional Government of Castilla y León granted permission to capture some specimens. Our thanks are also due to Begoña Tens for her help in the field.

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Supplementary Material

- Supplementary document 1. Source of the entomological collections used, country, study zone and identities.
- Supplementary document 2. Sampling sites of *Cordulegaster boltonii* adults in the Iberian Peninsula.